

In vitro* inhibitory effect of herbal organic formulations on mycelial growth of Pea wilt pathogen *Fusarium oxysporum

***W. Tampakleima Chanu, Bireswar Sinha, Kota Chakrapani**

Department of Plant Pathology, College of Agriculture, Central Agricultural University, Imphal, Manipur, India

*Corresponding email: tampakleima139@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Short Communication Received on April 03, 2020 Revised on April 14, 2020 Accepted on April 29, 2020 Published on May 06, 2020</p> <p>Article Authors W. Tampakleima Chanu, Bireswar Sinha, Kota Chakrapani Corresponding Author Email tampakleima139@gmail.com</p>	<p>The objective of this study was to determine inhibitory activities of three herbal organic formulations (fungidote, viridote, and bacteridote) on <i>in vitro</i> growth of <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> causing <i>Fusarium</i> wilt of a pea in Manipur. <i>In vitro</i> results showed that these formulations inhibited the mycelial growth of <i>F. oxysporum</i> in a dose-dependent manner. Fungidote was found to be the most in reducing mycelial growth compared to the other two formulations at different concentrations. These results underpin that formulations could be used in eco-friendly disease management of <i>Fusarium</i> wilt of a pea.</p>
PUBLICATION INFO	KEYWORDS
<p>International Journal of Agricultural Invention (IJAI) RNI: UPENG/2016/70091 ISSN: 2456-1797 (P) Vol.: 5, Issue: 1, Pages: 110-112 Journal Homepage URL http://agriinventionjournal.com/ DOI: 10.46492/IJAI/2020.5.1.16</p>	<p>Concentration, <i>Fusarium</i>, Formulations, Herbal, Pea</p>

HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE

Chanu, W. T., Sinha, B., Chakrapani, K. (2020) *In vitro* inhibitory effect of herbal organic formulations on mycelial growth of Pea wilt pathogen *Fusarium oxysporum*, *International Journal of Agricultural Invention*, 5(1): 110-112. DOI: [10.46492/IJAI/2020.5.1.16](https://doi.org/10.46492/IJAI/2020.5.1.16)

Pea (*Pisum sativum* L.) is an important leguminous vegetable crop grown throughout the world as winter annuals which require cool and humid climate (Smart, 2000). It occupies a position of considerable importance in the human diet as a source of rich digestible crude proteins, carbohydrates, vitamins, and minerals. It is also an important rabi pulse crop in the North-Eastern region of India. In Manipur, a north eastern hill state of India, rabi pulses were grown in about 27.07 Mha of the area producing 25.27 MT of pulses with 0.93 MT/ha productivity (Anon., 2017-2018).

Pea production is facing many biotic and abiotic threats among them biotic diseases constitute the most important factor that reduces average yield by a direct attack on the grains of the crop. The *Fusarium* wilt of pea was first recognized during 1918 by Bisby in Minnesota (Chupps and Sherf, 1960). In India, the first report of the occurrence of pea wilt organism was made available by (Patel *et al.*, 1949) from Bombay. Wilt of pea caused by *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *pisi* (Linford) Snyder and Hansen, is one of the most important diseases which can cause partial to complete losses of the crop (Basu *et al.*, 2004, Persson *et al.*, 2007).

It is one of the most common threats to pea production in Manipur also, having significant economic considerations. The disease is soil-borne, farmers acquiring synthetic chemicals to control fungal infection of pea and poses a greater problem in management by using chemicals that are uneconomical, and their frequent and indiscriminate use often leads to atmospheric pollution and development of resistance in the pathogens. In this background, an herbal organic formulation is an alternative approach to the control of soil-borne pathogens which is eco-friendly. This study focused on evaluating the phytotoxic activity of herbal organic formulation against the radial growth of *F. oxysporum*.

Materials and Methods

Identified *Fusarium oxysporum* (MH578602) isolates collected from wilt infested pea plants of Kongba (Imphal East District of Manipur) was used in the present study. The pure culture of isolated fungus was maintained on PDA slants and stored in the refrigerator for further investigations and sub-cultured at regular intervals. *In vitro* inhibitory action of three herbal organic formulations, namely Fungidote, Viridote and Bacteridote at different concentrations *i.e.*, 0.1%, 0.2%, 0.3% and 0.4% were evaluated against linear growth of *F. oxysporum* by poisoned food technique (Nene and Thapliyal, 2000).

The appropriate quantity of each formulation was separately dispensed in a molten sterilized PDA medium to make the desired concentrations for each formulation. 5 mm diameter mycelial blocks, taken from ten days-old culture of *F. oxysporum* were aseptically placed in the center of solidified poisoned PDA. Each treatment was replicated three times. The Petri-plates were incubated at 27±1°C and observations on the linear growth of test fungus were recorded after seven days of incubation. The growth of test fungus on non-poisoned PDA served as a control.

Per cent inhibition in mycelial growth was calculated by the following formula described by Vincent (1927)

$$PI \text{ (Per cent inhibition)} = \frac{C-T}{C} \times 100$$

Where,

C = linear growth of the fungus in control

T = linear growth of the fungus in treatment

Results and Discussion

In vitro testing of herbal organic formulations revealed that all formulations had a significant inhibitory effect on colony growth of the pathogen at different concentrations and the data are presented in table 1 and fig 1. Fungidote produced best inhibition at 0.4%, 0.3% and 0.2% concentrations with 63.14%, 57.65% and 53.53%. The mycelial growth inhibition was next followed by Viridote with 45.29% of inhibition at 0.4% of concentration and least inhibition was observed in Bacteridote with 22.74% inhibition at 0.1% of concentrations as compared to other treatments. There was an overall trend of reduction in mycelial growth of test fungus with an increase in the concentration of formulations.

The current results were under the findings of Chakrapani *et al.*, (2020) found that all ayurvedic formulations considerably inhibited the growth of *Rhizoctonia solani* and fungidote showed highest mycelial inhibition followed by viridote and bacteridote against *R. solani*. From the present findings, it is marked that the treatments of all the formulations used have some toxic principles which directly show their effect on the growth of the pathogen. Our results suggest that these formulations might be useful to reduce *Fusarium* wilt in pea fields.

Table 1. *In vitro* efficacy of herbal organic formulations on the growth of *Fusarium oxysporum*

S. N.	Treatments	Concentrations (%)	Inhibition over control (%)*
1.	Viridote	0.10	22.74 ⁱ
		0.20	36.47 ^g
		0.30	39.41 ^{fg}
		0.40	45.29 ^d
2.	Fungidote	0.10	40.98 ^{ef}
		0.20	53.53 ^c
		0.30	57.65 ^b
		0.40	63.14 ^a
3.	Bacteridote	0.10	25.10 ⁱ
		0.20	29.61 ^h
		0.30	36.47 ^g
		0.40	43.14 ^{dc}
S. E (d)±		-	1.56
C. D. (5%)		-	3.23

*Mean of three replications

Conclusion

Based on the present investigation it can be concluded that the herbal organic formulations could be a good alternative used for control of

Fusarium wilt of a pea. However, further work is needed to explore the potential of selected plants at the field level.

Fig 1. *In vitro* efficacy of herbal organic formulations on the radial growth (cm) of *Fusarium oxysporum*

References

Anonymous (2017-18) Area, production and yield in Manipur, Department of Agriculture, Government of Manipur, India.

Basu, P. K., Crete, R., Donaldson, A. G., Gourley, C. O., Haas, J. H., Harper, F. R., Lawrence, C. H., Seaman, W. L., Toms, H. N., Wong, S. I. and Zimmer, R. C. (1973) Prevalence and severity of diseases of processing peas in Canada, *Can. Plant Dis. Surv.*, **53**: 4.

Chupps, C. and Sherf, A. F. (1960) Vegetable disease and their control, The Ronald Press Company, New York, pp: 668.

Chakrapani, K., Sinha, B., Siram, T., Chanu, W. T., Chakma, T., Thangjam, B. (2020) *In vitro* sensitivity test of ayurvedic formulations against growth of *Rhizoctonia solani* causing sheath blight

of rice in Manipur, *Int. J. Agric. Invention*, **5**(1): 72-74.

Nene, Y. L. and Thapliyal, P. N. (1979) Fungicides in plant disease control, Oxford and IBH Publishing Co., Bombay, pp: 507.

Patel, M. K., Karnath, M. N. and Bhide, V. P. (1949) Fungi of Bombay: Supplement-I, *Indian Phytopathol.*, **2**: 142-155.

Persson, L. L., Bodker and Wikstrom, M. L. (2007) Prevalence and pathogenicity of foot and root rot pathogen of pea in Southern Scandinavia, *Pl. Dis.*, **81**: 171-174.

Smart, J. (2000) Grain Legumes: Evolution and Genetic Resources, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK.

Vincent, J. M. (1927) Distortion of fungal hyphae in presence of certain inhibitors, *Nat.*, **159**: 239-241.